

FACTORS EFFECTING UNIVERSITY STUDENTS' INTENTION TO USE E-LEARNING SYSTEM

YAP YU KI¹
NORMALA S. GOVINDARAJO²
Xiamen University Malaysia

ABSTRACT

Amid the COVID-19 pandemic, many sectors are experiencing drastic transformation in this challenging time to adapt and sustain themselves, including the education sector. According to Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), almost 83.3% of learners globally have been affected by this pandemic due to the restriction and lockdowns. Hence, educational sectors have been performing transition from physical class into e-learning to ensure that the teaching process can still be carried on. Taking into account that this scenario has made the frequency of online teaching higher, thus this thesis aims to find out the factors that affect the university students' intention to use the e-learning system. Past studies have extensively made research on the behavioral intention of students using e-learning systems, but little research was being made regarding this topic in Malaysia, especially for a higher educational institution. Hence, by referring to the previous Technology Acceptance Model 2 (TAM2) proposed by Davis and Venkatesh (2000), this study introduces a research framework that can be used to examine the intention of students using the e-learning system from different perspectives, such as academic relevancy and output quality of the system. This research also examines the moderating role of perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use on the students' intention to use online learning systems. The scope of the study is only 100 university students in 1 of the private university. Regarding the importance of this study, the analysis provides significant evidence of certain aspects that the higher educational institution should modify to improve their teaching system based on the opinion collected from the student's perspective. Furthermore, this study also provides insights for the higher education ministry to improve their policy and standards regarding the online learning system. The analysis concludes that all variables in the research framework influence students' intention to use e-learning among students.

Keywords: E-Learning System, Technology Acceptance Model 2, Behavioral Intention, Xiamen University Malaysia